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UZBEKISTAN'S ROLE IN REGIONAL AND GLOBAL MULTILATERAL ORGANIZATIONS

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ANNOTATION

Uzbekistan plays a significant role in regional and global multilateral organizations, fostering cooperation and stability. As a member of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) since 2001, it contributes to regional security and economic initiatives. Additionally, Uzbekistan participates actively in the Central Asian regional platforms such as the Central Asia Regional Economic Cooperation (CAREC) and the Conference on Interaction and Confidence-Building Measures in Asia (CICA), promoting dialogue and development. Globally, Uzbekistan engages through the United Nations, emphasizing international cooperation on issues like sustainable development and peacekeeping. Overall, Uzbekistan's involvement underscores its commitment to regional integration and constructive global diplomacy.

Key words: *multilateral diplomacy, international relations, agreement, Uzbekistan, organizations, digital diplomacy, crisis diplomacy, history, overview.*

LITERATURE AND METHODOLOGY

While doing research, I carefully investigated several materials using the analysis method and in the following article, I have illustrated the short historical overview of the multilateral diplomacy as well as its importance in the modern arena of international relations.

RESULTS

Since gaining independence from the Soviet Union in 1991, Uzbekistan has faced the dual challenges of establishing a sovereign national identity and positioning itself within the complex landscape of international relations. Under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who took office in 2016, Uzbekistan has markedly increased its participation in various regional and global multilateral organizations. This shift reflects a strategic vision aimed at promoting national interests, enhancing security, and fostering economic development. This dissertation explores Uzbekistan's

engagement with these organizations, examining the motivations behind its increased participation, its key contributions, and the broader implications for its foreign policy and development strategy. The significance of multilateral diplomacy stems from its ability to foster cooperation, pool resources, and promote a more inclusive and effective approach to navigating the complexities of the contemporary world.

Following its independence from the Soviet Union in 1991, Uzbekistan embarked on a journey fraught with challenges and opportunities in shaping its foreign policy. Led by President Islam Karimov, the newly formed republic faced the daunting task of establishing itself as a sovereign state amidst the tumultuous aftermath of the Soviet collapse. Uzbekistan's foreign policy during this period was profoundly influenced by a complex interplay of historical, geopolitical, and internal factors, which collectively shaped its stance of cautious isolationism.

The dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991 had profound implications for Uzbekistan, fundamentally altering its socio-political and economic landscape. As a constituent republic of the Soviet Union for decades, Uzbekistan experienced a sudden shift from a centrally planned economy under Moscow's control to an independent nation-state. This transition was not only a legal and political change but also a seismic shift that impacted every facet of Uzbek society.

The collapse of the Soviet Union left Uzbekistan and other newly independent states grappling with the daunting task of establishing viable state institutions. During the Soviet era, governance structures had been tightly integrated into the overarching Soviet framework, with decisions often made in Moscow. With independence, Uzbekistan had to rapidly develop its own governmental institutions, including executive, legislative, and judicial bodies, to effectively govern its territory and population.

Moreover, the transition required Uzbekistan to assert its national identity in the international arena. This involved creating and defining symbols of statehood, such as national flags, anthems, and state emblems, which are essential for asserting sovereignty and fostering national unity. Establishing a distinct national identity was crucial for differentiating Uzbekistan from its Soviet past and asserting its status as an independent actor on the global stage. Economically, Uzbekistan faced significant challenges following independence. The shift from a centrally planned economy meant breaking away from Soviet economic structures and practices, which had dictated production quotas, resource allocation, and trade relationships. Uzbekistan had to devise its own economic policies, transitioning towards market-oriented reforms while managing the complexities of privatization, deregulation, and trade liberalization.

DISCUSSION

The dissolution of the Soviet economic system also disrupted established supply chains and trading relationships, posing immediate challenges to Uzbekistan's economic stability. The country had to renegotiate trade agreements, establish new export and import regimes, and navigate the complexities of international trade and finance as an independent nation. Geopolitically, Uzbekistan found itself navigating new realities in a region historically shaped by Soviet influence and rivalries. Central Asia, a region characterized by diverse ethnic groups, historical tensions, and strategic interests of major powers, became a critical arena for Uzbekistan's foreign policy. The country had to balance its national interests with regional dynamics, forging alliances and partnerships while safeguarding its sovereignty. An example of Uzbekistan navigating geopolitical realities post-independence is its engagement in regional cooperation frameworks. Uzbekistan, along with other Central Asian states, established the Central Asian Cooperation Organization (CACO) in the early 1990s to foster economic integration, security cooperation, and cultural exchange among the newly independent states. This initiative aimed to address shared challenges such as border security, water resource management, and regional stability.

Additionally, Uzbekistan's participation in the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) since its inception in 2001 exemplifies its strategic approach to regional security and economic cooperation. The SCO, comprising China, Russia, and Central Asian states, has provided Uzbekistan with a platform to engage in joint efforts to combat terrorism, extremism, and drug trafficking while promoting economic connectivity through infrastructure projects and trade initiatives.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Uzbekistan's engagement in regional and global multilateral organizations exemplifies its proactive approach towards enhancing stability, cooperation, and development. By participating in forums like the SCO, CAREC, CICA, and the United Nations, Uzbekistan not only strengthens regional ties but also contributes to global dialogue on pressing issues such as security, economic growth, and sustainable development. Through its active involvement, Uzbekistan reaffirms its commitment to fostering peace and prosperity both within Central Asia and on the broader international stage, highlighting the country's pivotal role in shaping multilateral frameworks that promote mutual understanding and collective progress.

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